

Zoning of MPA for Saint Martin – Teknaf Peninsula through an Inclusive and Data Driven Approach

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Submitted by:

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Executive Summary

Marine protected area (MPA) is an effective tool for protecting critical coastal and marine habitats to recover, conserve and enhance species diversity, and build ecosystems resilience to environmental change. Having a biodiversity rich maritime area of 118,813 km², Bangladesh is facing the challenges of environmental change and over exploitation. Thus, conservation efforts are urgently needed for the coastal and marine ecosystems of Bangladesh. Taking this into account ECOFISH II during 2020 in collaboration with Shahjalal University of Science and Technology aimed to assess the suitability of the Naf – Saint Martin Peninsula of south-east coastal zone in Cox’s Bazar area of Bangladesh to delineate as MPA considering four protection levels. This research continued until December 2021 and this year study aimed to validate the identified potential MPA zones (during 2020) through stakeholder consultation, assess the possible impact of proposed potential MPA on community, and identify the AIGs and compensation option for the local communities. In addition, this study also analyzed the possible impact of proposed potential MPA on marine biodiversity and developed a marine spatial plan (MSP) for proposed MPA.

Based on stakeholder consultations the study identified 2,992.29 km² potential area of the Naf – Saint Martin Peninsula for MPA declaration with four restriction options (no-entry, no-take zone; entry, no-take; partial reserve and general reserve zones). Potential no-entry, no-take zone covers an area of 44.37 km² while entry, no-take; partial reserve and general reserve zones cover 710.92, 1436 and 801 km² areas, respectively. The stakeholder mentioned that MPA can decrease power and causes alienation from natural resource management, increase social vulnerabilities, force migration from their age old profession, increase conflict, restriction, social tension and poverty, loss of assets and social and educational facilities. However, to make the MPA initiative successful local communities need to offer the alternative income generating activities. This study identified 14 such types of activities (i.e. seaweed farming, fish farming, handicraft, livestock rearing, small scale business, agriculture, job, mechanical works, dairy product preparation and crab fattening). The study found that increasing fishing pressure significantly reduced the species biomass while reduced fishing pressure increased the biomass of species. Biomass of the species in the system with no fishing area increased significantly (3 – 6%) while compared with the species biomass of an area without fishing restriction. Numerical

simulations found that imposing fishing restriction in an exploited system significantly improve the species standing stock. The model outputs suggest that declaration of MPA is beneficial for conservation of biodiversity. However, for sustainable implementation of conservation initiatives a proper management framework is necessary integrating diverse stakeholders.

Figure 6.5 Sustainable fishing zone in the proposed Naf – Saint Martin MPA

Figure 6.6 Government imposed fishing ban area (left), and mangrove and mud flat (right) of Teknaf coast

6.2.6. Sustainable tourism zone

Sustainable tourism zone is located in the water area around the Saint Martin's Island (Figure 6.7). However tourism should be developed in such a way that its impact on ecosystem is not adverse (Begum, Sarker, Uzzaman, Shamsuzzaman, & Islam, 2020; Chowdhury et al., 2021; Horn et al., 2021; M Shahadat Hossain, Chowdhury, Sharifuzzaman, & Sarker, 2015; M. S. Hossain et al., 2020; M. Shahadat Hossain, Sarker, Sharifuzzaman, & Chowdhury, 2020; M. Shahadat Hossain et al., 2021; M. Shahadat Hossain et al., 2019; Masud-Ul-Alam, Sarker, Khan, Rahman, & Mahmud, 2021; Nelms et al., 2021; Subrata Sarker, 2018; Subrata; Sarker, Ara Hussain, Assaduzzaman, & Failler, 2019; Subrata Sarker, Lemke, & Wiltshire, 2018; Subrata Sarker, Masud-Ul-Alam, Hossain, Rahman Chowdhury, & Sharifuzzaman, 2021; Subrata Sarker, Panassa, et al., 2020; Subrata Sarker & Wiltshire, 2017; Subrata Sarker, Yadav, Akter, et al., 2020; Subrata Sarker, Yadav, Hossain, et al., 2020).

Figure 6.7 Sustainable tourism zone in the proposed Naf – Saint Martin MPA

Chapter 7

7.1. Conclusion

MPAs are an effective tool for protecting critical coastal and marine habitats to recover, conserve and enhance species diversity and build ecosystem resilience to environmental change. St. Martin's Island is the only coral reef island that has been classified as an Ecologically Critical Area in Bangladesh's 118,813 km² EEZ. The area is rich in biodiversity, including unique reef fish and megafauna that cannot be found anywhere else in Bangladesh. The coral habitat itself has more than 900 species, including some critically endangered, endangered and vulnerable species, with special measures needed for conservation and rehabilitation. However, this critical habitat and unique biodiversity are facing challenges from environmental change and overexploitation of fisheries resources and megafauna. As the unique habitat supports a wide range of reef fish and other fauna and flora, a holistic ecosystem-based management approach is essential to manage it sustainably.

The declaration and ecosystem-based management of an MPA is an approach that protects and maintains biological diversity, as well as associated cultural resources, in dedicated spaces in the ocean. This is done by imposing restrictions on human activities through legal and other effective means to achieve long-term conservation of ecosystems and cultural values. Moreover, due to the increase in local residents, who mainly rely on these coral-based resources and tourism, conservation efforts are urgently needed to conserve the unique ecosystems and supporting biodiversity to reduce the effects of these impacts. As such, the MPA proposal is an important, timely initiative to sustainably manage the unique coral habitat and its rich biodiversity, especially the colorful reef fish as well as megafauna, such as sharks, skates, rays, turtles and dolphins. Through sustainable biodiversity conservation and management, fish production would increase and the socioecological resilience of fishers would improve. Taken together, these actions would protect and restore this unique coral habitat. Finally, by declaring this 2845 km² an MPA, the country would add another 2.4% toward its target of having 10% of its EEZ declared as MPAs (M. Shahadat Hossain & Sarker, 2013; M. Shahadat Hossain, Sarker, Sharifuzzaman, & Chowdhury, 2013).

The jurisdiction for declaring the proposed Teknaf–St. Martin's Island MPA would fall under the Marine Fisheries Act 2020. The proposed MPA can be declared

under the Section II, Clause 3, Sub-Clause 2 of the Act. Under this clause, the government can declare a certain area for conservation of fisheries resources and can impose different levels of restrictions. The Department of Fisheries (DOF) could propose the declaration of the MPA, the Ministry of Fisheries and Livestock (MOFL) would be the lead ministry, and the Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change would be the associated ministry.

7.2 Recommendations on management measures

- Process the proposed new MPA area for declaration under the Marine Fisheries Act 2020 (Clause 3) instead of the Wild Life Conservation Act 2012.
- Ensure stakeholder engagement, focusing on the DOF, MOFL, Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change, law enforcement agencies, local administration, local leaders and fishers.
- Strictly follow the four zones as proposed, with different levels of restrictions, for the proper management of the resources and habitats.
- Formulate and implement a holistic approach of conserving the biodiversity and habitat, with a focus on fisheries and megafauna and an emphasis on conserving critically endangered, endangered or vulnerable species.
- Address the conservation of aquatic and shore birds, with special care paid to nesting and parental care requirements.
- Take special care to improve the nesting migration, nesting success and hatching success of the sea turtles, as the proposed area is their most important nesting hub.
- Regulate the number of tourists and tourist activities in such a way that ensures no significant impact on resources and habitats.
- Stop the extraction of coral completely, and regulate and minimize seaweed collection.
- Water pollution, especially plastic and abandoned nets, is harmful and acts as a silent killer of coral reef organisms, so reducing those materials must be a priority.
- Higher carbon and temperatures due to climate change accelerate the acidification of coral organisms, so reducing impacts through rehabilitation and/or conservation of the habitat through forestation needs to be done with greater importance.

- Allow new homes and rehabilitate current ones in a safe zone to reduce the human impacts on this unique coral habitat.

7.3. Way forward

- Hold a stakeholder consultation on MPA management.
- Formulate a detailed management action plan (MAP) considering marine spatial planning and the ecosystem approach for fisheries management.
- Take necessary steps to officially approve the formulated MAP.
- Engage all stakeholders through co-management for implementing the MAP.
- Monitor the progress and impact of implementing the MAP through a proper monitoring, evaluation and learning process.

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